

ICARE Approach for Designing Online Learning Module Based on The Ubiquitous Learning Class

Evi Hanizar

Universitas PGRI Argopuro Jember, (Indonesia)

Eges Triwahyuni

Institute Teacher Training and Education of PGRI Jember, (Indonesia)

Atan Pramana

Universitas Negeri Surabaya, (Indonesia)

Online learning started with the emergence of internet technology and has been increasingly used during the COVID-19 pandemic. However, it has raised many problems, such as limitations in presenting material (monotonous and uninteresting), building activeness and difficulty creating interaction between lecturers and students and between students. Moreover, online learning is more stressful than regular classroom sessions because students have to study alone. The absence of clearly structured learning steps also makes it difficult for them to focus. Therefore, this research aims to develop an independent online learning module with a structured and systematic flow called Introduce, Connect, Apply, Reflect and Extend (ICARE) based on the ubiquitous classrooms. Furthermore, it determines the eligibility of the module using a ADDIE design for education which consists of analysis, design, development, implementation, and evaluation. All stages resulted in an eligible online module with an u-learning class ICARE flow in the Learning Media course.

Keywords: ICARE approach, online learning module, u-learning class

1. Introduction

Learning systems worldwide, including in Indonesia, were forced to change completely during the Covid-19 pandemic. Before the pandemic, certain schools, colleges, and training institutions rarely conducted online learning. However, this changed during the pandemic because schools and universities have implemented many online-based learning policies. This is a quick response to minimize the Covid-19 transmission.

Online learning is practical and flexible because it is conducted anywhere

(Kadek Suartama, Setyosari, et al., 2020; Suartama et al., 2019, 2020). However, it causes many unique problems for lecturers and students during the pandemic. Most lecturers and students are not ready for online learning because they are unfamiliar with its technology and strategies (Churiyah et al., 2020). (Irfan et al., 2020) stated that the challenges faced in online learning include limitations in material presentation (monotonous and uninteresting), building activeness, and creating interaction between lecturers and students and among students. Moreover, it is more stressful than regular classroom sessions because students have to study alone. The absence of structured and systematic learning steps also makes it difficult to focus (Yusnilita, 2020). Online content is theoretical and mediocre and does not allow students to practice and study effectively (Dhawan, 2020). Furthermore, mastery learning cannot be completed online M. (Adnan, 2020).

The previous studies are a reference in overcoming the obstacles lecturers, and students face in online learning to make it more interesting and meaningful. Lecturers must innovate in new learning methodologies that they did not prepare before, by integrating technology as one of the main tools to convey knowledge into strategies and teaching materials (Almonacid-Fierro et al., 2021). Also, pedagogy is a determining factor in intentions, behavior, and success in online learning. It includes clear and structured learning strategies, the provision of richer content or teaching materials, and an environment that improves student performance (Hao et al., 2017). Students learn in different ways with various modalities. Providing various media options for students and giving clear learning steps ensures they continue learning (Dhaliwal & Kim-Sing, 2018). However, systematic planning is needed to determine and define these pedagogical aspects in a module design.

Learning modules are teaching materials arranged systematically and attractively. They include material content, methods, and evaluations for independent use to achieve the expected competencies (I. Anwar, 2010). Learning modules are currently divided into three categories. The first category is the conventional or physical teaching materials, such as books and other prints. The second category comprises electronic teaching materials accessed through electronic devices, such as cellphones, tablets, PCs, and laptops that store the module. The third category consists of online teaching materials accessed through electronic devices anytime and anywhere, provided there is an internet network (Phillips et al., 2015).

Online learning modules are teaching materials arranged systematically, are measurable, attractive, and easily understood by users. They are accessible and used without space and time barriers, provided there is an internet network (Arasaratnam-Smith & Northcote, 2017), (Vrasidas et al., 2010). Therefore, they are accessed using gadgets such as cellphones, tablets, and PCs, or laptops. Moreover, online learning materials are built from various meaningfully

integrated resources (Hill et al., 2015). In line with this, online modules enable interactive learning, assessment, and adaptive feedback (Phillips et al., 2015). They are designed to support students' independent learning in diverse environments (Mamun et al., 2020).

The transition from face-to-face to online teaching materials is a challenge because lecturers are no longer present in real-time to assess and direct students' learning. Therefore, its effectiveness strongly correlates with the module organization and the clarity of the written information provided, and the learning steps (Cobb et al., 2018). It is necessary to design modules with the structured or systematic steps applicable in large classes and promote and enable students to reflect on the subject content and formulate their thoughts before sharing them privately (G. Basilaia and D. Kvavadze, 2020), (M. H. Taha, M. E. Abdalla, M. Wadi, and H. Khalafalla, 2020).

2. Literature Review

Education is a long-term investment in human resources (HR) which has strategic value for the continuity of human civilization in the world (Cayrat & Boxall, 2023). So, a teacher is a crucial part of education. In the context of education, teachers play a significant and strategic role. This is due to the fact that educators are leading the way in putting education into practice (Oviyanti, 2016; Reuge et al., 2020; Reyes-Cortés et al., 2018) The process of learning involves communication between students, instructors, and instructional materials. Without media or a way to transmit the message, communication cannot take place. Thus, in order to raise students' competency, efforts must be made to enhance the learning process by utilizing media or instructional materials based on information technology (Abdulrahman et al., 2020; David & Weinstein, 2023).

The Industrial Revolution 4.0 has brought changes in various aspects of human life technologically from the current generation and the traditional methods used in teaching and learning, educators at all levels will find it more difficult to improve the teaching and learning experience in the classroom (Dwivedi et al., 2023). The development of technology, information and communication in the 4.0 revolution can help in learning activities which provide a new atmosphere in change activities (Javaid et al., 2022; Javed et al., 2019) The learning process has an influence on achievement in education because learning is a process of interaction between students and learning resources in a learning environment. The existence of learning resources has an important role in achieving student learning goals (Far & Pattiasina, 2021; Wahyuningsih et al., 2021). Learning resources are various or all sources in the form of data, people and certain forms that can be used by students in learning activities either separately or in combination, making it easier for teachers to achieve their learning goals (Darling-Hammond et al., 2020). Therefore,

teachers are required to be more creative and innovative in teaching materials for the current learning process (Mawaddah & El-yunusi, 2024)).

The earlier research serves as a guide for overcoming the challenges that instructors and students have when attempting to make online learning more engaging and significant. By using technology as one of the primary tools for knowledge transfer into strategies and instructional materials, lecturers must innovate in new learning methodologies that they were not previously prepared for (Almonacid-Fierro et al., 2021). Additionally, the success of online learning, behavior, and intentions are all influenced by pedagogy.

It consists of providing richer information or teaching materials, employing organized and unambiguous learning methodologies, and creating an atmosphere that enhances student performance (Hao et al., 2017). Students use a variety of modalities and learn in different ways.

The educational resources in learning modules are structured in an appealing and methodical manner. To attain the required abilities, they consist of assessment tools, techniques, and content for independent application (I. Anwar, 2010). There are now three categories for learning modules. The traditional, tangible instructional resources, such books and other printed materials, make up the first group. The electronic instructional materials in the second category can be accessible via electronic devices, including laptops, PCs, tablets, and cellphones that store the module. Online instructional resources are included in the third category and can be accessible via electronic devices at any time and location as long as there is an internet connection (Phillips et al., 2015).

Online learning modules consist of systematically organized educational resources that are measurable, visually appealing, and simple for users to understand. If there is an internet network, they can be utilized and accessed anywhere, at any time. As a result, devices like laptops, PCs, and tablets are used to access them. Furthermore, a variety of purposefully integrated resources are used to create online learning materials (Hill et al., 2015). Accordingly, interactive learning, assessment, and adaptive feedback are made possible via online modules (Phillips et al., 2015). In a variety of settings, they are intended to assist students' autonomous learning (Mamun et al., 2020). Because instructors are no longer in the classroom in real time to monitor and guide students' learning, the shift from in-person to online learning presents challenges. As a result, the effectiveness of online learning heavily depends on how well modules are organized, how easily understood the written material is, and what steps students must take to complete the material (Cobb et al., 2018). Modules must be designed with steps that are structured or systematic enough to be used in large classes, and they must encourage and enable students to reflect on the material before expressing their ideas in private.

Introduce, Connect, Apply, Reflect, and Extend (ICARE) is a learning

model showing systematic and structured learning steps. This model is applicable in making and directing students to be more active in learning and draw conclusions from the lessons (Rizal et al., 2020). Furthermore, it ensures that students apply what they have learned, making learning more meaningful (Latifa et al., 2020) Online modules are developed using the Ubiquitous Learning Class (u-Learning) (Dhaliwal & Kim-Sing, 2018). (Perkins, M. & Pfaffman, 2006) stated the benefits of u-Learning that allows lecturers to easily send assignments, lesson plans, announcements, and other learning documents. This research uses the Moodle LMS because it increases students' involvement in online learning and positively influences their thinking and innovation skills (K. Georgouli, I. Skalkidis, and P. Guerreiro , 2008), (Chootongchai & Songkram, 2018).

3. Method

Research Design

This study uses the Research and Development (R&D) for Education method to produce an online learning module and test its eligibility (W. R. Borg and M. D. Gall, 1983). The steps taken in developing the module with an u-learning class based ICARE flow were adapted from the development model proposed by Lee, (W. W. Lee and D. L. Owens, 2004). They include Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation (ADDIE) stages. This model is used because it has been tested, complete, and simple.

Procedures

Referring to the research design and development models selected, the procedure for developing an u-learning class based online module with ICARE flow is described in Table 1.

Table 1. Steps for Development of Online Module with u-learning class based ICARE flow

No	Step	Activity
1.	Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Need assessment, identifying problems causing <u>unoptimal</u> learning processes and outcomes b. Front-end analysis, identifying student characteristics, infrastructure, and facilities as online learning supports, and environment conditions c. Conducting instructional analysis, including mapping of competencies or learning objectives to be mastered by students
2.	Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Determining the need for computer equipment (hardware and software) b. Determining learning materials or resources and strategies or activities c. Designing and mapping the resources and activities in the u-learning class into the ICARE stage in the form of a program mapping
3.	Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Creating an online module this step consists of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (1)Creating a portal by obtaining a server or Webhosting, choosing a category, and creating and elevating user status (2)Creating a Learning Media course with steps: 1) create and change course settings, 2) enter resources (Page, Label, File, Book, Folder, IMS Content Package, URL), and 3) create an activity (Lesson, Chat, Forum, Assignments, Feedback, Choice, Database, Glossary, Quiz, Survey, Wiki, Workshop, SCORM, LTI/External Tool) b. Product validation by material or content and media experts c. Conducting product revision
4.	Implementation	Conducting trials on students
5.	Evaluation	Final revision and product evaluation

Product Validation and Trial

The developed product’s eligibility is determined through validation by one material or content expert (lecturer for Learning Media course) and one media expert (doctorate in educational technology). Furthermore, the product is tested on 80 Universitas PGRI Argopuro Jember students taking the Learning Media course. The data obtained from the validation and trial activities are then analyzed and used to improve or perfect the developed product.

Data Collection

A questionnaire was used in the product validation and trial activities. The right data were obtained using quality instruments that explore what is desired. The quality instruments were obtained by analyzing documents, making specification tables (grid), consulting with experts (material and media) and colleagues, and writing instruments.

The questionnaire filled out by the material expert is prepared based on

the theory of principles and perspectives for designing learning software (D. F. Walker and R. D. Hess, 1984). Furthermore, the questionnaire filled out by the media expert adapts to comprehensive standards or rubrics for online learning design (Debattista, 2018). Meanwhile, the questionnaire filled out by students in the trial activity is prepared based on assessing the material and media experts. This involves selecting the statements or questions relevant to students of the developed product users. This questionnaire has open-ended and closed-ended questions or statements. Open-ended questions ask for opinions or suggestions from experts and students on the developed product, while closed-ended statements are prepared using a 5-point Likert scale. Tables 2 and 3 present the instrument grids of material and media experts.

Table 2. Grid of Learning Material Assessment Instrument

Assessed aspect	Indicator
Material Aspect	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Suitability of the material with the competency formulation - Concept truth - Order of material presentation - Suitability of the given example - Adequacy/completeness of materials - Material updates
Learning Aspect	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clarity of learning objective formulation - Accuracy of learning indicators - Giving motivation - Giving training - Suitability of images, videos to clarify the material
Language Aspect	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Suitability of language with student development level - Spelling and grammar accuracy - Accuracy of terms - Language simplicity - Ability to arouse students' curiosity

Table 3. Grid of Online Learning Media Assessment Instrument

Main Standards	Specific Standards	
Course opening	- Description - Behavior - Role - Accessibility	- Integrity - Technical competences - Ownership
Instructional resources for teaching and learning	- Openness - Provision - Entitlement	- Application - Variety - Academic integrity
Interaction and community	- Peer learning - Fostering	- Management
Learner support	- Academic - Instructional	- Administrative - Technical
Technology design	- Interface - Access - Centricity	- Investment - Authentication - Management
Course closing	- Conclusions - Archiving	- Resolution
Assessment of learning	- Measurement - Grading	- Management - Feedback
Instructional design cycle	- Academic	- Administrative - Technical

4. Data Analysis

The research used qualitative data, comprising criticisms, inputs, and suggestions from validators and students collected and summarized for product improvements. Also, it used quantitative data in the form of scores obtained from each instrument item. The descriptive statistical analysis technique provided the value or quality of the developed online module. The scores obtained were added up, averaged, and converted using a 5-scale criterion-referenced test table (Sukardjo, 2010), as shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Conversion of Scores into Values on a Five Scale

Formula	Score	Value/Category
	Calculation	
$X > \bar{X}_i + 1,80 S_{bi}$	$X > 4,21$	Very good
$\bar{X}_i + 0,60 S_{di} < X \leq \bar{X}_i + 1,80 S_{di}$	$3,40 < X \leq 4,21$	Good
$\bar{X}_i - 0,60 S_{di} < X \leq \bar{X}_i + 0,60 S_{di}$	$2,60 < X \leq 3,40$	Quite good
$\bar{X}_i - 1,80 S_{di} < X \leq \bar{X}_i - 0,60 S_{di}$	$1,79 < X \leq 2,60$	Bad
$X \leq \bar{X}_i - 1,80 S_{di}$	$X \leq 1,79$	Very bad

Description:

$$\text{Ideal mean } (\bar{X}_i) = 1/2 \times (\text{maximum score} + \text{minimum score})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Ideal standard deviation (Sdi)} &= 1/6 \times (\text{maximum score} - \text{minimum score}) \\ \text{Maximum score} &= 5 \\ \text{Minimum score} &= 1 \\ \bar{X}_i &= 1/2 \times (5+1) = 3 \\ \text{Sdi} &= 1/6 \times (5 - 1) = 0,67 \\ X &= \text{Actual score} \end{aligned}$$

The following formula is used to find the mean score in assessing the developed product:

$$\bar{X}_i = \frac{\sum X}{n}$$

Description:

\bar{X}_i = Mean score

$\sum X$ = Total score

n = Number of validators/respondents

A minimum "good" eligibility value is determined through assessment by the material and media experts. The developed online learning module is eligible for application when the final (overall) assessment receives a "good" score from the experts.

5. Results

Online Learning Module Design

The online module design with an ICARE flow based on the u-learning class displays digital learning stages and materials. The learning steps are the ICARE model stages, consisting of introduction, connection, application, reflection, and extend. Materials include document (doc, pdf, xls, txt), presentation (ppt), picture (jpg, gif, png), video (mpg, wmv), sound (mp3, au, wav), and animation (swf, gif). The learning steps and materials are arranged as a program mapping for easy accessibility and use when developing online modules. In this regard, program mapping is a table with learning steps and materials, where each component has an interconnected link (Kadek Suartama, Setyosari, et al., 2020). The program mapping of the online module with ICARE flow based on Moodle LMS contains a description of learning steps, types of materials, and u-learning class features, comprising resources and activities, as shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Program Mapping of Online Learning Module with ICARE flow based on The u-Learning Class

ICARE Flow	Type of Learning Material	u-Learning Features	
		Resource	Activities
Introduction - Providing an understanding of the lecture content to students. - This section explains the course objectives and what is to be achieved by the course.	- Document (pdf) - Presentation (ppt)	- Page - File	- Lesson - Forum
Connection - Connecting new teaching materials with something familiar to students. - Conducting simple brainstorming exercises to understand what students already know - Students tell what they remember from previous lectures or by developing activities they are able to carry out themselves. - Lecturers connect students' prior knowledge with new information through presentations or simple explanations.	- Document (doc, pdf) - Presentation (ppt) - Picture (jpg, png) - Video (mpg)	- Book - File - URL	- Lesson - Assignments - Chatting - Feedback - Google meet - Messages - Assignments - Feedback
Application - Students are allowed to practice and apply new knowledge and skills. - Students work individually, in pairs, or in groups to complete real activities or solve problems using the new information and skills acquired.	- Document (pdf) - Presentation (ppt) - Animation (swf) - Video (mpg) - Multimedia (exe)	- File - URL - IMS content package	- Forum - Assignments - Chatting - Feedback - Google meet - Messages - Assignments - Feedback
Reflection - Students make presentations or write about what they have learned from the summary of learning outcomes. - Giving exploratory quizzes/questions to students with several choices adapted to conditions	- Document (pdf) - Presentation (ppt)	- File - URL - Label - Page	- Lesson - Feedback - Workshop - Assignments - Quiz
Extend - Students read additional teaching materials, assignments, or exercises to strengthen and expand the completed subject matter.	- Document (pdf) - Presentation (ppt)	- File - URL - Label - Page	- Lesson - Feedback - Assignments

Final Product

The online module as the final product of this development research is accessed at <https://u-learningclass.site/course/view.php?id=2>. The Learning Media course as the research object is categorized in the Second semester Educational Technology Study Program. This course consists of six modules with different topics on learning media. They include basic concepts, classification, characteristics, management, selection, and development of learning media.

Figure 1 shows that each module follows the systematic stages of the ICARE (Introduction, Connection, Application, Reflection, and Extend) flow. The Introduction consists of learning instructions, basic competencies, indicators, learning objectives, and learning materials. It provides students with an understanding of how to learn, the competencies to be achieved, and the content of learning materials. This introduction is built by utilizing the Lesson feature of the u-learning class, which allows students to navigate each page regularly. The learning materials section contains files (pdf, ppt, mpg, swf, exe, etc.) according to each module's topic.

Connection is performed synchronously through the web meeting feature (video conference). This stage provides apperception by connecting new teaching materials with something familiar to students. In this case, connection involves holding a simple brainstorming exercise to understand students' knowledge and asking them to state what they remember from the previous lecture. The lecturer then connects the students' prior knowledge with new information through presentations or simple explanations. Furthermore, Application is conducted to allow students to practice and apply new knowledge and skills. Students work individually, in pairs, or in groups to complete activities or solve real problems using the new information and skills acquired. Additionally, activities at this stage are facilitated by Student Worksheets with case-based (module 2) and project-based learning (module 6) methods using the assignment u-learning class feature.

Reflection is conducted to check or ensure what students have learned by presenting a learning outcome summary. This stage utilizes web conferences and gives students exploratory quizzes or questions with several choices adapted to conditions. The features used in the u-learning class LMS are web meetings (video conference) and Quiz. Subsequently, Extend is conducted to strengthen and expand the completed subject matter by reading additional teaching materials, assignments, or exercises using the URL u-learning class feature. One online lecture activity was conducted within seven days (for example: lectures are scheduled for Monday, the range of activities is Monday to Sunday). Students were free to carry out activities, such as gathering assignments, conducting forums and quizzes within those seven days. There was no scheduling of certain days and specific times to carry out online lectures between course professors and students. Activities in online learning are downloading teaching materials, forum, quiz/training (weekly), chatting, this activity is not required to be carried out by lecturers or students participating in the course; it is only a complement to activities in online learning (Kadek Suartama, et al., 2020).

The developed online module has shown the systematic and structured learning steps through which students study the material independently according to their preferences. Furthermore, they expand their knowledge by researching what they learn from learning activities and become responsible for understanding (Salirawati et al., 2020). The learning stages in this module contain an invitation to make students more familiar with the material being studied. Also, it stimulates the emergence of their critical attitude towards the material. This means that ICARE accommodates many applications of the topics studied in everyday life. Additionally, it provides assignments that require students to find answers through various resources (Sinuraya et al., 2020).

Product Eligibility

After internal testing to ensure the product runs smoothly, it is evaluated through validation by material and media experts and trial to students. Figure 2 presents the expert validation and product trial results.

Figure 2. Results of Product Validation and Field Trials

The data in Figure 2 shows that the mean score for the overall product assessment by the material expert is 4.36. This figure is "Very Good" according to the conversion table of quantitative to qualitative data on a five scale. Therefore, the material developed is eligible to be applied in learning. Moreover, two revisions or improvements were made based on suggestions from the material expert. First, advanced material obtained from learning resources was added by utilization. Second, students were presented with problem-or project-based learning materials that enable them to think critically and creatively.

The mean score for the overall product assessment by the media expert is 4.84. This figure is "Very Good" according to the conversion table of quantitative to qualitative data on a five scale. Therefore, the developed media is eligible for application in learning. Similarly, three revisions or improvements were made based on suggestions from the media expert. First, various learning resources were added to accommodate different student modalities. Second, instructions were added to each module to assist students in self-study. Third, discussion forums were added to train students in critical, creative thinking and fostering communication or collaborative skills.

The mean score for the overall online module assessment in the learning media course by students is 4.65. This figure is "Very Good" according to the conversion table of quantitative to qualitative data on a five scale. Therefore, the product developed is eligible for application in learning.

Based on student comments in the product trial, learning becomes more

flexible because online modules are accessed anytime and anywhere. Furthermore, systematic learning steps help accelerate the understanding of module content. Students also admitted that enrichment materials provide broader insight into the subject matter. They evaluate the learning progress from feedback and grades provided immediately by the lecturer. Moreover, online modules are easier to use and highly accessible, making learning more efficient.

The assessment by experts and students in the "Very Good" category is due to the steps and aspects considered and used in developing this online learning module. The online module with an u-learning class based ICARE flow in this Learning Media course was developed through five stages, including analysis, design, development, implementation, and evaluation. This process was quick and smooth because it is based on the pre-made plans and supported by the readiness of the required materials according to the analysis results.

The eligibility of an online module with an u-learning class based ICARE flow in the Learning Media course is achieved because the presentation follows structured steps. These steps lead to maximum student activity to seek and find material (they become study subjects). The results of the research by (Yudiawan et al., 2021) stated that an online learning system and environment designed with clear stages can guarantee the success of learning. Subsequently, students not become passive recipients but construct their knowledge according to their pace in the learning process. Furthermore, all student activities involve seeking information and answers to their problems, fostering self-confidence, and developing higher intellectual abilities (Bada & Olusegun, 2015). Therefore, the online module with an u-learning class based ICARE flow in the Learning Media course minimizes negative activities in online learning. Furthermore, it presents choices of media or resources developed by the lecturers (learning resources by design) or using available materials (learning resources by utilization). These include a document (doc), presentation (ppt), animation (swf), video (mpg), and multimedia (exe), which accommodate student modalities. Consequently, this allows students to learn in ways that suit them and promote their activeness (I. K. Suartama, et al., 2021)

6. Discussion

This module has also facilitated virtual synchronous learning through video or web conferences. Additionally, it has enhanced personal asynchronous through assignments, quizzes, and chats, as well as collaborative interpersonal through online discussion forums and team-based project-based worksheets. There are also variations in delivery and teaching methods, as well as lecturer-student and student-student interactions. These variations provide benefits, such as flexibility, productivity, efficiency, and achievement (Araújo et al., 2017), (Munawaroh, 2017). Similarly, selecting the u-learning class Moodle LMS application to build an online module has provided several advantages. First,

there is flexibility in determining learning activities, such as surveys, communities, journals, assignments, quizzes, choice questions, and chats. Second, various formats of learning activities are available, including topic, weekly, and social. Third, the module is capable of displaying various user activities. Fourth, all class members on assignments, journals, quizzes, and forums are viewed on one page and downloadable as spreadsheet files.

Based on student responses in the trial activity, the online module with the u-learning class based ICARE flow in the Learning Media course has clear learning stages and good interactivity. Therefore, it makes students interested and active in the learning process, an indicator of their motivation, and a good sign towards improving outcomes (Kadir Demir, 2018). The attractive display elements of this product include the home page, ease of navigation, and a harmonious blend of text colors and backgrounds. Additionally, this module in each subject is equipped with pictures, animations, videos, and multimedia, helping students or users understand the material better. Enrichment activities (extend) accommodate students with a good speed and completeness in learning.

The ease of using the online module with the u-learning class based ICARE flow on this Learning Media course is also recognized by students. They use this module by typing the URL: <https://u-learningclass.site/course/view.php?id=2> in the browser and accessed with a mobile device or smartpone. Through this module, materials are accessed more quickly, anytime, and anywhere. Furthermore, materials enriched with various learning resources, including course media, are quickly updated by lecturers. This environment was constructed by carrying out the following: (1) integrating various instructional delivery methods/models and learning styles, (2) introducing several choices of media/resources and formats of interaction between instructors and students, (3) implementing many features, such as chat, forums, and video conferences. It also provided students with the opportunity to experience the knowledge construction phase, especially in sharing/comparing information. In addition, students were able to share experiences or opinions, express agreement with others, provide supportive examples, and ask and answer questions to clarify statement details (Suartama et al., 2024). (Karasneh, 2022) indicates that paradigms shifts will assist both students and universities by enhancing achievement and learning.

Outcomes and encouraging them to remain competitive with various educational outlets and improve performance students also carry out monitoring, communication, and cooperation. Additionally, they download materials, take assignments and quizzes, and participate in chats and discussion forums. However, despite its many advantages, some obstacles are faced in this online module, especially for students limited to electronic devices, such as PCs, laptops, or smartphones, or demand good internet access.

Research Limitations and Future Research Recommendations

The Online modules with the ICARE flow based on u-learning class is limited on, the application must use a computer or mobile device, requiring adequate internet access, limited to learning media course materials, the evaluation carried out in this study did not reach the (long-term) impact evaluation stage, assessment of learning outcomes in u-learning class is only limited to cognitive aspects.

Based on the findings and discussion of the results of this study, the recommendations that can be given are:

- Online modules with the ICARE flow based on u-learning class in the Learning Media course need to be implemented in the second semester group of the UNIPAR educational technology department as the main target in the learning media lecture.

- For students who are using u-learning for the first time, lecturers should give directions on how to use the u-learning even though it is designed for independent learning for students.

- This Online modules with the ICARE flow based on u-learning class can be disseminated through academic seminars organized by the university, through training activities on learning media, collaboration with learning centers, educational and training institutions, and other various forums so that e-learning is developed, and used by many people who need, especially related to the introduction of media.

- Efforts should be made to develop online modules with the ICARE flow based on u-learning class by optimizing more varied presentation methods.

- Further research activities need to be sought to identify the effectiveness of the use of u-learning class products both with classroom action research methods and experimental research in a broader target group.

7. Conclusion

Online learning modules are systematically arranged teaching materials, measurable, attractive, and easily understood by users. They are accessed and used without space and time barriers, provided they are connected to the internet network. Subsequently, these modules are accessed using gadgets, such as cellphones, tablets, and PCs or laptops. The online module with an u-learning class based ICARE flow in this Learning Media course was developed through analysis, activity design development, learning resources, evaluation, and validation from experts. Moreover, the online module was assessed on various aspects, including instructional design, course opening, learning, as well as interaction and community. The other aspects assessed were instructional teaching and learning resources, learner support, technology design, course

closing, and instructional design cycle. The results were "very good" category, meaning that this product is eligible for application.

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Declarations

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

The authors declare that this work was exempt from review from an IRB/Ethics board.

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